

The reliable energy storage for all climates and households

Minimal Size Thermal and Electrical Energy Storage System for In-Situ Residential Installation

MiniStor, a Horizon 2020 project, introduced a high-density thermal storage system for multiple climate conditions and home configurations, providing heating and cooling in an integrated yet flexible unit.

Seventeen partners across the European Union and Switzerland, coordinated by IERC, developed and tested MiniStor through heating and cooling seasons in one pre-pilot and four demonstration sites across the European Union, following the most rigorous standards.

OBJECTIVES

Reliable thermal energy storage operating year-round for energy security

High-performance, flexible unit providing heating and cooling

Minimal size, integrated and scalable solution for existing and new homes

For multiple building configurations and climatic conditions

User-centric tool for comfort and building energy efficiency

Improving renewable sources usage and energy consumption

Circular business model to enhance sustainability and lifecycle support

Improving standards for efficiency, installation and operation

CONCEPT

MiniStor prototype

3550 mm x 2450 mm x 2700 mm (LxWxH)
Weight around 2.5 t

The system combines a thermochemical storage and a phase-change material that stores latent heat for a thermal storage density of 213 kWh/m³, over ten times that of water. This minimal size, scalable installation envisioned by CERTH/CPERI and CNRS-PROMES is delivered by Sofrigam and Psycoterm.

Unique solar hybrid photovoltaic thermal (PVT) collectors reach the required heat and generate

electricity for a battery. ENDEF's PVT panels include glazed collectors, for a laminate of 265Wp, and unglazed collectors, with 390Wp.

The operation is handled via the Home Energy Management System (HEMS), a smart digital tool by CARTIF. Alongside an Internet of Things platform by CERTH/ITI, it considers demand and generation predictions to help in decision-making.

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